

Determination of Iron in Different Phases in Chondritic Meteorites by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry

N. R. SEN GUPTA and A. N. CHOWDHURY

Central Chemical Laboratory, Geological Survey of India, Calcutta.

Manuscript received 1 March 1976 ; accepted 10 May 1976

An analytical procedure for the separate determinations of different forms of iron coexisting in the metallic, sulphide and silicate phases in chondritic meteorite have been described. The procedure has been developed on the basis of successive quantitative dissolution of the meteorite sample first with ammonium-mercuric-chloride at the boiling temperature in CO₂-atmosphere to dissolve iron present in the metallic phase, next with the mixture of bromine-anhydrous methanol at room temperature to dissolve iron present in the sulphide phase and finally decompose the sample left with HF-HClO₄ acid treatment for a solution of iron present in the silicate phase. The iron is then determined from the solutions obtained by the successive chemical treatments by the atomic absorption spectrophotometric procedure. The atomic absorption spectrophotometric procedure for iron is accurate and permits the determination of iron in the phasewise solution of the chondritic meteorite in presence of large quantities of mercury salts and other interfering elements.

THE complex nature of the chondritic meteorite creates a number of special analytical problems in the analysis. These problems arise due to the presence of the three phases i. e., (i) metallic phase, (ii) sulphide phase and (iii) silicate phase coexisting in the chondritic meteorites¹. Iron can exist in each of these phases and it is essential to determine iron present in different phases in order to evaluate the chemical composition of the chondritic meteorites.

In most of the existing scheme of analysis of chondritic meteorite only iron in metallic phase is determined along with the total iron in the meteorite sample^{2,3,4}. The distribution of iron between phases is computed from the analytical data on iron (metallic), total S and total iron in the magnetic and non magnetic fraction^{1,5}. Hence none of the earlier analytical procedure could provide for the independent determination of iron in metallic, sulphide and silicate phases. Therefore it has been felt necessary to develop an analytical procedure for the determination of iron in metallic, sulphide and silicate phases individually and independently so that the mineral species and the chemical composition of the chondritic meteorite may be properly evaluated from the analytical data without making any assumption

The analytical procedure developed for this purpose is based on the selective phase-wise dissolution of iron from the meteorite sample by successive chemical treatment first with ammonium-mercuric-chloride at the boiling temperature in CO₂-atmosphere to dissolve the metallic phase only, secondly with bromine-anhydrous methanol at room temperature to dissolve the sulphide phase and finally with HF-HClO₄ to decompose the silicate phase. The iron passing into solution in the successive chemical treatment is determined by the

atomic absorption spectrophotometric procedure. The atomic absorption spectrophotometric procedure for iron estimation is accurate and permits the determination of iron in the phase-wise solution of the meteorite sample in presence of large quantity of mercuric salts in addition to the other within tolerance limit of interfering salts⁴.

The proposed analytical procedure has been applied for phase-wise determination of iron in two chondritic meteorites i. e., Desuri meteorite and Sitathali meteorite⁶ and the results obtained are recorded.

Experimental

Apparatus : Atomic absorption spectrophotometer used is of Perkin Elmer 303 model fitted with iron hollow cathode lamp. An acetylene-air lean flame was used for the determination of iron. The other instrumental parameters are maintained as given in the instrumental manual.

Standard iron solution (stock solution mg Fe/ml) : Standard iron solution is prepared from the Spec. pure iron filings. Weighed amount of iron filings (0.250 g) is dissolved in 1 : 1 nitric acid. About 5 ml of HClO₄ are added and the solution is slowly evaporated to fumes. The fumed mass is cooled to room temperature and transferred to 250 ml volumetric flask. The volume is made upto the mark with distilled water.

Appropriate dilution is carried out from the standard stock solution.

Procedure :

(a) **Determination of iron in metallic phase :** 0.250 g. of the powdered meteorite sample (≈ 100 mesh)

is weighed out in a conical flask and is treated with ammonium-mercuric-chloride (6 g. of HgCl_2 with about 3 g. of NH_4Cl in 50 ml distilled water) in CO_2 -atmosphere at a boiling temperature for about an hour. After the reaction is complete, it is filtered and the residue is washed with hot water thoroughly. The filtrate is collected in 250 ml volumetric flask. After cooling, the solution is made upto the mark with distilled water. This solution or the suitable diluted solution is then aspirated into the flame of atomic absorption spectrophotometer maintaining the instrumental parameters and the experimental conditions for the estimation of iron as described in the operational manual. A reference curve is obtained by the similar conditions of experiments from the standard iron solution. The reference curve is a straight line and the concentration of iron in the unknown solution is obtained from the reference curve.

(b) *Determination of iron in sulphide phase* : The residue left after the mercuric chloride treatment is washed with anhydrous methanol and then transferred to the same conical flask. It is treated with bromine-anhydrous methanol solution (1 ml of Br_2 in 50 ml of anhydrous methanol) at room temperature for about 30 min. The mixture is shaken occasionally. This is then filtered, washed with anhydrous methanol till the residue is free of bromine. The filtrate is evaporated nearly to dryness. 5 ml of HClO_4 is added and the mixture is slowly evaporated to the fumes of perchloric acid. The mass is taken up with distilled water to dissolve the salts and transferred to 250 ml volumetric flask and the volume made upto the mark with distilled water. Iron is determined from this solution by the atomic absorption spectrophotometric procedure as described above.

(c) *Determination of iron in silicate phase* : The residue, after treatment with Br_2 -methanol, is transferred to a platinum basin and is ignited. The ignited mass is moistened with 5 ml of water and is treated with HF-HClO_4 (5 to 10 ml of HF and 5 ml of HClO_4). The mixture is slowly evaporated to fumes and thoroughly for about 2 to 3 min. The fumed mass is cooled somewhat, 1 to 2 ml of HClO_4 is added and then dissolved in 50 ml of water. The solution is transferred to 250 ml volumetric flask and the volume is made upto the mark with distilled water. Iron is determined from this solution or suitable diluted solution by the atomic absorption spectrophotometric procedure as described above.

The results are recorded in the table.

TABLE—1

Sample	%Fe* (total)	%Fe (Metallic phase)	%Fe (sulphide phase)	%Fe (silicate phase)
Desuri- meteorite	27.86	15.92	3.36	8.65
Sitathali- meteorite	24.29	10.62	3.32	10.30

*Total iron is estimated by the standard wet chemical procedure in the meteorite sample.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that the total iron value obtained by the conventional method on the meteorite sample is quite nearer to the sum total of iron value obtained by determining the iron value individually and independently in the different phases of the meteorite sample by the atomic absorption spectrophotometric procedure. Moreover, the chemical composition derived from the analytical data obtained by this procedure is in close agreement with the petrological data of these samples⁵ indicate that nearly the quantitative extraction of iron by the successive chemical treatments of the meteorite samples are achieved. Iron determined by treatment with ammonium-mercuric-chloride corresponds to the metallic phase which is present in the chondritic meteorite as an alloy of Ni-Fe. Iron determined by treatment with Br_2 -methanol corresponds to the sulphide phase present as sulphide mineral, troilite (FeS) and iron determined in HF-HClO_4 fraction corresponds to the iron in the silicate phase. The determination of iron in the three phases is important as the classification of chondritic meteorite for high-and low-group⁷ (Urey's classification) is based on the iron present in metallic phase plus sulphide phase against the iron present in the silicate phase. Hence the procedure described in this communication has got importance in the classification of the chondritic meteorites besides the evaluation of the chemical composition of the meteorites as the value of iron in coexisting phases of the chondritic meteorites are obtained accurately and independently through experiments and are not based on any computation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Director General, Geological Survey of India, for his kind permission for publishing the paper.

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